

**THE ROLE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH
AND ITS EFFECTS TO THE PROCESS OF LEARNING FOREIGN
LANGUAGES.**

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ABSTRACT

Technology has been used to help and improve language learning. Technology allows teachers to customize classroom activities, thereby improving the language learning process. Technology continues to increase its importance as a tool to help teachers make language learning easier for their students. This article explores how technology provides students with easy-to-access information, accelerated learning, and exciting opportunities to put what they learn into practice. It also allows students to explore new topics and learn in detail how to effectively convey challenging concepts.

Keywords: Digital platforms, mobile learning, **the IWB (interactive white board), Dogme (or materials-light teaching)**, Information and Communication Technology (ICT).

**INGLIZ TILI O`QITISHDA ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALARNING
O`RNI VA UNING CHET TILLARINI O`RGANISH JARAYONIGA
TA`SIRLARI.**

ANNOTATSIYA

Texnologiya til o'rganishga yordam berish va yaxshilash uchun ishlatilgan. Texnologiya o'qituvchilarga sinfdagi faoliyatni moslashtirishga imkon beradi va shu bilan til o'rganish jarayonini yaxshilaydi. Texnologiya o'qituvchilarga o'z o'quvchilari uchun til o'rganishni osonlashtirishga yordam beradigan vosita sifatida ahamiyatini oshirishda davom etmoqda. Ushbu maqola qanday qilib texnologiya talabalarga oson kirish mumkin bo'lgan ma'lumotlar, tezlashtirilgan o'rganish va o'rganganlarini amaliyotda qo'llash bo'yicha qiziqarli imkoniyatlarni taqdim etishini

yoritib beradi. Bundan tashqari talabalarga yangi mavzularni o'rganishga va qiyin tushunchalarni samarali yetkazib berish yo'llarini batafsil bilib olishga imkon beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Raqamli platformalar, mobil ta'lim, IWB (interaktiv doska), Dogme (yoki materiallar – yengil ta'lim jarayoni), Axborot va Kommunikatsiya Texnologiyalari (AKT).

INTRODUCTION

Language arose from the need for communication. Foreign languages in the last century grammatical, pronunciation, and conscious comparison techniques were used in teaching. In the age of modern technology, the study of foreign languages is also advancing that is, the use of new innovative technologies is on a consistent path set. In today's fast-paced world, science and technology are in full swing is growing. Development in every field is moving forward. In particular, significant changes are taking place in science as well. Every science delivery to students using new innovative pedagogical technologies is one of the basic requirements of education today.

The use of new technologies in the educational process has become increasingly important in recent years. It is not just new technological tools, but also new instructional styles and methods, as well as a new approach to learning. The primary goal of using modern technologies in foreign language learning is to demonstrate how technology can be effectively used to improve the quality of teaching foreign language students, the formation and development of their communicative culture, and learning the practical mastery of a foreign language. It is becoming so obvious that different approaches and techniques which can assist English language students to improve their learning skills by using technology. Among these techniques are online English language learning web sites, computer assisted language learning programs, presentation software, electronic dictionaries, chatting and email messaging programs, listening CD-players, and learning video-clips. The use of information and communication technology (ICT) into education results in the development of new learning paradigms. We live in a society that technology has

reduced to a global village, and technological advances are supporting pedagogical approaches. As a result, it may become necessary to reconsider how to alleviate the limits of second language users through the use of new technologies. The connections between new technology and pedagogical contributions have been discovered to fulfill the diverse demands of second language learners to some level, and any global finding aimed at lowering learners' limits is a desirable development in a quickly changing technological world. The rapid rise of ICT in the world's technologically advanced nations has assisted them in overcoming some of the barriers to teaching and learning. Applications of modern-day technologies in the field of teaching and learning can enable teachers, students, and others to join communities of people far beyond their immediate environment to critically review, analyze, contribute, criticize, and organize issues logically and contextually, with professionalism and societal transformations in mind.

Now, new technologies such as reported computer upgrades with new software and networking make it much easier for educators to overcome place and time, with the goal of alleviating restrictions and academic clashing concerns. Previously, learning and education merely meant attending face-to-face lectures, reading books or printed handouts, taking notes, and completing tasks in the form of answering questions or writing essays. In summary, education, learning, and teaching were thought to be impossible in the absence of a teacher, books, and chalkboards. Education and training have taken on entirely new meanings in the modern day. Computers are a crucial element of any classroom, and teachers use DVDs, CD-ROMs, and movies to demonstrate how things function and operate to students. Pupils can interact with the subject matter by using web-based tools and CD-ROMs. Furthermore, each student can advance at his or her own speed. Technology enables remote learning: Perhaps the most significant impact of technology in the field of learning is its ability to allow several people to learn at the same time from various locations. Learners are not forced to congregate at a specific time or location to learn and receive instructions and information. All that is required is a computer linked to

a modem (or with a CD drive); these technologies can literally deliver a "classroom" in people's homes and offices.

English language teaching is always evolving, especially as technology progresses. Here we have tip-notch technologies to revolutionize the process of learning English:

Digital platforms: When we talk of innovation, we frequently think about the internet and what we can now do online. Teachers like Facebook and, in particular, Edmodo, which provides a safe online space for teachers, students, and parents to connect. Cloud-based applications such as Google Docs have also become indispensable. It's 'where I've transferred so much of my individual and (because of its usefulness) collaborative writing with kids...' says teacher Tyson Seburn. The number of digital platforms is expanding all the time. A multimedia manual, such as Digital Video by Nik Peachey (nominated for an ELTons award for innovations in teacher resources), can assist teachers in navigating the complex, and at times overwhelming, world of digital resources, allowing teachers to create activities, lessons, and courses from a variety of sources.

The IWB (Interactive white Board): It first appeared in schools in the early twentieth century and has since become a standard in many classrooms in the United Kingdom and around the world. It enables us to save and print board notes, manage the classroom computer from the whiteboard, play listening exercises through the sound system, utilize the screen as a slide for presentations, access the internet, and so on. The possibilities appear to be limitless. However, adding an IWB to a classroom does not guarantee a superior learning experience. Indeed, unless teachers use them to supplement teaching and learning, they are merely a distraction.

Discovering the Dogme approach to language education was 'galvanising' for teachers like Matthew Noble. Dogme is a communicative method that rejects published textbooks in favor of conversational dialogue between students and teachers. It represents a shift from a one-size-fits-all approach to classroom materials. For many teachers, this 'unplugged' approach promises a fresh method of

approaching lesson content, as well as the opportunity to move away from self-contained language points and devote more time to student-generated language.

PLATO (Programmed Logic for Automatic Teaching Operations), the best-known tutorial system, is a special hardware consisting of extensive drills, grammatical explanations, and translation tests at various intervals. The next stage, communicative CALL, appeared in the late 1970s and early 1980s. It focused on the communicative teaching method and encouraged pupils to generate original utterances through the process of discovery, expression and development rather than just repeat the prefabricated language. Pupils were supposed to make use of the computer or the hardware to assist them in language learning. What they actually work with is not the computer but their classmates or teachers. In this model, the computer is viewed as stimulus or tool. Popular CALL software developed in this period included word processors, spelling and grammar checkers. Following this stage is the third stage, integrative CALL which included the development of multimedia computers and the Internet. This model not only integrates various skills (e.g. listening, writing, speaking and reading) but also bonds different technologies serving as effective and comprehensive tools for language learning and teaching. With integrative CALL, teachers were moving away from communicative perspective of teaching to a more social way, which emphasizes the language use in authentic social environments. Applying this multimedia networked computer in the language class provides pupils a more effective means to learn English. For instance, pupils can have rapid access to the background, grammatical or vocabulary explanations, pronunciation information while the main lesson is in the foreground. Besides, pupils under this model are usually encouraged to engage in their own language development rather than learn in a passive way.

CONCLUSION

As advances in technology drive globalization and digital transformation, teachers can help students acquire the necessary skills to succeed in the careers of the future. By integrating technology into existing curricula, as opposed to using it solely as a crisis-management tool, teachers can harness online learning as a powerful

educational tool. The proper use of digital learning technologies in the classroom can boost student engagement, assist teachers in improving lesson ideas, and enable personalized learning. It also assists pupils in developing critical 21st-century abilities. Virtual classrooms, video, augmented reality (AR), robots, and other technology tools can not only make class more interesting, but they can also create more inclusive learning environments that foster collaboration and inquisitiveness while also allowing teachers to collect data on student performance. However, it is crucial to remember that technology is a tool for education, not an end in itself. The promise of educational technology lies in what educators do with it and how they use it to best meet the needs of their students.

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